

Project acronym: EVERSE
Grant Agreement Number: 101129744
Project full title: European Virtual Institute for
 Research Software Excellence
Call identifier: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01

D6.1 Project Handbook and Sustainability Plans for Outputs

Version: 1.0
 Status: Submitted
 Dissemination Level: Public
 Due date of deliverable: 30.06.2024
 Actual submission date: 27.06.2024
 Work Package: WP6 Project Management & Coordination
 Lead partner for this deliverable: CERTH
 Partner(s) contributing: BSC CNS

Main author(s):

Name: Elena Bakoglidou	CERTH
Name: Laura Portell Silva	BSC CNS

Abstract

This document provides an overview of the management and administrative procedures of the EVERSE Project in order to facilitate efficient project execution as well as high-quality project results. It contains a concise reference to the project management structure, the project management procedures, tools and tasks, as well as the reporting procedures, including roles and responsibilities and project monitoring.

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Author(s)
0.1	22.04.2024	Initial draft by CERTH	Fotis Psomopoulos, Elena Bakoglidou, Aspa Orfanou, Nikos Pechlivanis
0.2	24.05.2024	Additional content and review by BSC CNS	Laura Portell Silva, Salvador Capella Gutiérrez
0.3	10.06.2024	Review and feedback by all	MB members
1.0	21.06.2024	Consolidation of feedback and final version by CERTH	Elena Bakoglidou

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Introduction	6
2 Project general overview and timings	7
3 Project Structure	8
3.1 Project Coordinator (PC).....	9
3.2 General Assembly (GA).....	10
3.3 Project Management Team (PMT).....	11
3.4 Management Board (MB).....	11
3.5 Work Package Leaders (WPLs).....	12
3.6 Scientific Advisory Board (SAB).....	13
4 Project Management Procedures and Tools	15
4.1 Contact and mailing lists	15
4.2 ownCloud	16
4.3 Website, Slack and social media.....	16
4.4 Design manual, templates, and project slide deck.....	17
4.5 Newsletter	18
4.6 Meetings.....	18
4.6.1 Face-to-Face meetings (and hybrid)	18
4.6.2 Online meetings	19
4.6.3 European Commission (EC) Project Review meetings.....	20
4.7 Participation in external events	21
4.8 Conflict of Interest.....	21
4.9 Emergency Procedure.....	21
4.10 Quality Control and Assurance.....	21
4.10.1 Project results, expected outcomes and expected impacts.....	21
5 Project Monitoring.....	23
5.1 Project Follow-up Strategy	23
5.1.1 Follow-up of Deliverables	25
5.1.2 Follow-up of Milestones.....	29
5.1.3 Follow-up of the Use of Resources.....	31
5.2 EC Periodic Reports	32

6 Risk Management	33
7 Intellectual Property Rights and Knowledge Management	35
8 Acronyms and Abbreviations	36
9 Annexes	37
9.1 Staff effort per participant	37
9.2 Project Months – Calendar months	38
9.3 Work Packages, Tasks, Deliverables	39

LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES

Table 1. EVERSE Partners	8
Figure 1. Management components	9
Table 2. Work Package Leads and co-Leads	13
Table 3. Mailing lists	15
Table 4. Summary/overview of project meetings	20
Table 5. Summary of the Results, Expected Outcomes and Expected Impacts	22
Figure 2. GANTT Chart	24
Table 6. List of Deliverables	26
Figure 3. Summary of Deliverable Review Process	28
Table 7. List of Milestones	29
Figure 4. Summary of Milestones Review Process	30
Table 8. List of Critical Risks and Mitigation Measures	33
Figure 5. Summary of Risk follow-up strategy	34

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides an overview of the management and administrative procedures of the EVERSE Project in order to facilitate efficient project execution as well as high-quality project results. The document will provide a concise reference to the project management structure, the project management procedurestools and tasks, as well as the reporting procedures, including roles and responsibilities, and monitoring of project progress. The potential risks of the project and how they can be dealt with are also described in this document.

1 Introduction

The Project Handbook aims at providing an overview of the internal management procedures for the EVERSE project, to ensure efficient project execution and high-quality project results. Planning the management procedure contributes to the management objectives of the project and indirectly influences all technical project implementation by providing an appropriate working environment.

This document provides the necessary information to project partners to facilitate the day-to-day management of the project, ensuring the project outcomes are delivered on time, within the budget, and expected quality. The handbook will be used as a guideline for the partners during the life cycle of the project.

The Project Handbook will be regularly updated throughout the lifetime of the project, and the last updated version will always be available in the internal repository "Consortium\3.Deliverables\".

2 Project general overview and timings

These are some key facts about EVERSE:

- ▶ **Project name:** European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
 - ▶ **Call:** HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01
 - ▶ **Topic:** HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-02
 - ▶ **Budget:** 6,789,468.75 €
 - ▶ **Duration:** 36 months
 - ▶ **Project starting date:** 1 March 2024
 - ▶ **Project end date:** 28 February 2027
 - ▶ **Project timeline:**
 - ▶ **Reporting Period 1 (RP1):** M1-M18
 - ▶ **Reporting Period 2 (RP2):** M19-M36
 - ▶ **1st Periodic Report:** due M20*
 - ▶ **2nd and Final Periodic Report:** M38*

**60 days after end of reporting period*

For ease of reference, relevant project information details have been gathered in the following tables as [Annexes](#) to this document:

- ▶ [Staff effort per participant](#)
- ▶ [Project months - Calendar months](#)
- ▶ [Work Packages, Tasks, Deliverables](#)

3 Project Structure

The Consortium is constituted by the following 18 partners, which includes 1 International Organisation and 2 Associated Partners (AP), with different organisational cultures (universities, research centres) that contribute with complementary expertise:

No	Title of the Organisation	Acronym	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	BSC CNS	ES
3	ORGANISATION EUROPEENNE POUR LA RECHERCHE NUCLEAIRE	CERN	CH
4	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	CNRS	FR
5	FRIEDRICH-ALEXANDER-UNIVERSITAET ERLANGEN-NUERNBERG	FAU	DE
6	THE SQUARE KILOMETRE ARRAY OBSERVATORY	SKAO	UK
7	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	ELIXIR	DE
8	UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM	UvA	NL
9	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM DRESDEN-ROSSENDORF EV	HZDR	DE
10	STICHTING NETHERLANDS ESCIENCE CENTER	NLESC	NL
11	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	ES
12	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA	UNIPD	IT
13	UNIVERSITA DEL SALENTO	UNILE	IT
14	OPENAIRE AMKE	OPENAIRE AMKE	EL
14.1	ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS	ARC	EL
15	UNIVERZITA KARLOVA	CU	CZ
16	THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	UEDIN	UK

17	THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER	UNIMAN	UK
----	------------------------------	--------	----

Table 1. EVERSE partners

The management structure for the project is designed to provide an appropriate level of professional management to mediate efficiently between the different interests and cultures of the partners, and it is based on well-known best-practice methodologies.

The project organisational structure is based on the following key components:

- ▶ Project Coordinator (PC)
- ▶ General Assembly (GA)
- ▶ Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)
- ▶ Project Management Team (PMT)
- ▶ Management Board (MB)
- ▶ Work Package Leaders (WPLs)

Figure 1. Management components

The interactions between the different management components are described in the following sections.

3.1 Project Coordinator (PC)

The Project Coordinator (PC) is the intermediary between the project partners and the Granting Authority (European Commission, EC) and performs all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the PC gathers and submits all the deliverables and any specifically requested documents to the EC Portal, chairs the General Assembly and coordinates the EC Review meetings.

3.2 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) is the formal decision-making body that holds the highest level of authority in the project. It is chaired by CERTH (as Project Coordinator) and is coordinated in collaboration with BSC CNS. It consists of one representative from each partner and is formally responsible for successful project completion.

As described in article 6 of the Consortium Agreement, the GA will make decisions by consensus when possible. In the case that consensus cannot be obtained, the GA will put decisions to a vote and decide by a simple majority. In the event of a tie vote, the GA chair will cast the deciding vote.

The GA will meet at least once a year during the lifetime of the project, either face-to-face and/or online, to review the project's progress (further details in section 4.6 below).

The GA will be responsible for the final approval of changes in resource allocations, the Description of Action (DoA), and for the review and approval of the EC Periodic Reports.

CERTH and BSC CNS, as coordinators of the General Assembly, will convene the ordinary meetings of the GA (trying to accommodate the Work Package Leaders availability), giving prior notice no later than 14 calendar days preceding the selected meeting date. They will be responsible for compiling and distributing the meeting minutes summarising the actions agreed upon and the next steps.

3.3 Project Management Team (PMT)

The Project Management Team (PMT) is the body responsible for overseeing the project execution ensuring effective and efficient coordination to deliver the project goals, benefits, and expected impact within time, scope, budget and with high quality.

It is composed by CERTH as coordinator and BSC CNS as the project support team.

3.4 Management Board (MB)

The Management Board (MB) is composed by the Project Management Team (PMT) and the Work Package Leaders (WPLs) (see members below).

The MB is responsible for the day-to-day execution of the project, ensuring coordination across Work Packages (WP), the timely delivery of project objectives and outputs, and the continuous monitoring of the project's progress.

The MB is also in charge of the implementation of any decision affecting the description of the action or resource allocation, previously approved by the GA.

In particular, the MB is responsible for:

- ▶ Supervising the overall execution of the project activities, in particular by overseeing the completion of Deliverables, Milestones, and the risk register, as described in Section 5.1 below.
- ▶ Ensuring proper coordination among and within Work Packages

- ▶ Monitoring the internal use of resources to ensure efficient distribution and expenditure of EU funding (see Section 5.1.3 below).
- ▶ Reviewing and contributing to the EC Reports (periodic and final reports) before submitting them to the European Commission.
- ▶ Assisting with the preparation of both the EC Mid-term and End of Project Reviews.
- ▶ Identifying deviations in the project plan to elaborate contingency measures that will have to be approved by the GA.

To achieve these goals, CERTH and BSC CNS will organise and coordinate the MB by setting up regular meetings (ideally monthly, or at least once every three months), setting up the agenda, and distributing meeting minutes that will include the next steps.

In the event of not reaching a consensus among its members, the decision will be escalated to the GA and brought to a vote if necessary.

3.5 Work Package Leaders (WPLs)

Work Package Leaders (WPLs) are responsible for the scientific and technical work of their respective WPs. This includes:

- ▶ Planning and control of all activities within their Work Package (including tasks, deliverables, milestones, risk management, and mitigation measures).
- ▶ Coordination and implementation of their own WP regular meetings. They meet regularly, either online or face-to-face, and arrange additional ad hoc technical meetings when necessary.
- ▶ Preparation of Deliverables and the collection of all partners' contribution for internal and external reports.

During the **MB meetings**, they are expected to:

- ▶ Give an **update on the WP progress** status in the dedicated section for WP updates in the monthly MB minutes document.
- ▶ Identify relevant information to be uploaded to the **project website** (see section 4.3 below).
- ▶ Raise critical issues encountered and coordinate **cross-Work Package** relationships within the appropriate activity area.

Each WPL is appointed by the organisation responsible for the respective WP. The following table contains the names of each WP Leader and co-Leader as described in the Grant Agreement:

WPs	WP Leaders/Co-Leader	Time frame
WP1	CERN/ ELIXIR Hub	M01-M36
WP2	BSC CNS/ NLeSC	M01-M36
WP3	CNRS/ UEDIN	M01-M36
WP4	HZDR/ UniMan	M01-M36
WP5	CERN/UPM	M01-M36
WP6	CERTH/ BSC	M01-M36

Table 2. Work Package Leads and co-Leads

If there are any changes to the appointed persons, the PMT must be informed accordingly (by sending an email to elenabak@certh.gr).

3.6 Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)

The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) will be set up by M6 and shall be comprised, as described in the GA, by the following distinguished members and others:

- ▶ Anna-Lena Lamprecht (University of Potsdam)
- ▶ Andrew Goetz (ESRF)
- ▶ Michelle Barker (ReSA)
- ▶ Daniel S. Katz (Un. Illinois Urbana-Champaign)
- ▶ Andreas Kosmider (Falling walls foundation)

The SAB is expected to provide advice for the identification of exploitation opportunities of the project results and will have access to all project deliverables. Its feedback will help to track technical issues and potential risks.

In particular, the SAB mission is to give feedback on the project's plans and analyse the project results to ensure appropriate strategic alignment with the ECs expectations and the cancer data ecosystem beyond the project. This input will be particularly valuable prior to official project reviews with the EC. To facilitate this, drafts of the Reporting Period reports will be provided to the SAB in advance.

CERTH, as coordinator of the Scientific Advisory Board, will be in charge of organising the SAB meetings at key strategic project points (e.g., before the EC review meetings corresponding to the end of RP1 and RP2 periods) and for writing the minutes to submit them to the General Assembly; BSC CNS will give support. The SAB members shall be allowed to participate in General Assembly meetings upon invitation but have no voting rights.

The SAB will meet at least twice during the project's lifetime, coinciding with the annual GA or one of the technical meetings.

4 Project Management Procedures and Tools

The project management procedures and tools describe all the internal communication strategies set in place for a smooth and effective project implementation and follow-up.

4.1 Contact and mailing lists

All partners' contact details are compiled in a contact list that is available in the ownCloud folder.

All partners are advised to keep their own section updated and inform via email elenabak@certh.gr of any changes introduced into the table.

A set of **mailing lists** have been created with the aim to support the cooperation among all partners and encourage participation in the decision-making process.

Mailing lists	
General Assembly (all)	everse@lists.certh.gr
Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)	everse-sab@lists.certh.gr
Management Board (MB)	everse-mb@lists.certh.gr
General Assembly Pls (PMT)	everse-ga@lists.certh.gr
Administration	everse-admin@lists.certh.gr
Finance	everse-financial@lists.certh.gr
Legal	everse-legal@lists.certh.gr
Outreach	everse-outreach@lists.certh.gr
WP-Leaders	everse-wpl@lists.certh.gr
WP1	everse-wp1@lists.certh.gr
WP2	everse-wp2@lists.certh.gr
WP3	everse-wp3@lists.certh.gr
WP4	everse-wp4@lists.certh.gr
WP5	everse-wp5@lists.certh.gr
WP6	everse-wp6@lists.certh.gr

Table 3. Mailing lists

These mailing lists can be of special importance to the WP Leaders when planning their Work Package internal meetings.

Requests to add new members to the mailing lists should be processed by sending a request to elenabak@certh.gr and by filling out this form <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EVERSE> in order to comply with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) rules.

If any team member/participant wishes to unsubscribe, an email should be sent to the address that appears in Table 3 above, with a copy to elenabak@certh.gr.

4.2 ownCloud

CERTH has set up a specific tool, the ownCloud shared folder, to facilitate the exchange of project documentation among partners.

ownCloud is a secure and trusted data exchange service for researchers and scientists that helps them keep their research data synchronised and up to date. Furthermore, this service aims at ensuring that everyone has access to the latest and updated project documentation while providing an online space to simultaneously collaborate and edit working files. For any problem accessing the shared folder, please contact CERTH (fpsom@certh.gr, elenabak@certh.gr).

ownCloud shared folder has the following folder's structure:

- 01** – Official Project Documentation
- 02** – WPs 1-6
- 03** – Deliverables & Milestones
- 04** – Reporting
- 05** – Meetings groups
- 06** – Communication
- 07** – Other Documents

All partners are kindly requested to upload to the correspondent folders all project relevant documentation. Particularly, all Work Package Leaders and co-Leaders shall keep their own WP folders updated with the information related to their sub-folders:

4.3 Website, Slack and social media

As part of the communication and dissemination goals of the project (as set out in WP1), CERN has created a dedicated website and the following social media accounts:

- ▶ **EVERSE website:** <https://everse.software/>
- ▶ **GitLab Mattermost:** <https://mattermost.hzdr.de/everse> (Signup via: https://mattermost.hzdr.de/signup_user_complete/?id=c866a5ft1tyg9yti6xq4s6a6mr&md=ink&sbr=su)
- ▶ **Indico:** [EVERSE Indico \(cern.ch\)](https://cern.ch/EVERSE-Indico)

- ▶ Social media:
 - ▶ X (formerly know as Twitter): https://twitter.com/eosc_everse
 - ▶ LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-everse>
 - ▶ FOSStodon: https://fosstodon.org/@eosc_everse
 - ▶ Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/everse/>

Work Package Leaders will be requested during the Management Board meetings to identify any relevant information regarding their WP progress that shall be published on the website and/or posted on the social media accounts. Any changes in official partner social media accounts, as well as contact persons for communication issues, should be communicated immediately to CERN: graeme.andrew.stewart@cern.ch with cc sanje.antona.fenkart@cern.ch for CERN and nikosp41@certh.gr for CERN.

For further details on the Outreach and Communications Strategy, please refer to Deliverable 6.3.

4.4 Design manual, templates, and project slide deck

In the ownCloud shared folder “Consortium\6.Communication\Logos\” there are all the information regarding the project logos and the main colours that shall be used in the project (with their codes).

To help consolidate the visual image of all project outcomes, partners are kindly advised to use any of the following templates that have been developed by CERTH:

- ▶ Deliverable template
- ▶ Milestone report
- ▶ PowerPoint

Note: it is very important to make a copy of the template document before starting to work on them (otherwise the template document will be lost for others' edition).

The templates are available in the ownCloud shared folder "Consortium\6.Communication\Project templates"

4.5 Newsletter

In order to ensure project efficiency, transparency, and visibility among its members, a periodic newsletter will be distributed to the Consortium.

The newsletter will gather updates on:

- ▶ The progress of each Work Package
- ▶ The progress of each Milestone
- ▶ Submitted Deliverables
- ▶ Upcoming meetings
- ▶ Latest project activities and social media highlights
- ▶ Calls for participation in social media campaigns
- ▶ Calls for identification of external events for dissemination
- ▶ Other

This Newsletter will be coordinated by CERTH, with the support of CERN and BSC.

4.6 Meetings

The project has different types of meetings:

- ▶ Consortium internal meetings:
 - Face-to-Face meetings (and hybrid)
 - Online meetings
- ▶ EC Project Review meetings

4.6.1 Face-to-Face meetings (and hybrid)

The first Face-to-Face (F2F) meeting was the Kick-off Meeting (KoM) organised by CERTH on 11-13 March 2024 in Thessaloniki (Greece), aiming at establishing the basis of the project and agreeing on the first 6-month

tasks. The presentations and the meeting minutes are available in the internal repository in the ownCloud shared folder “Consortium\5.Meetings\Kick-off-Meeting”.

Besides, the project plans to organise a General Assembly F2F meeting at least once a year. The exact dates and the venue are yet to be confirmed.

For these F2F meetings, the hosting partner will be responsible for organising the meeting venue, and paying for the conference facilities and the catering, if any. The attendees are expected to pay for their own travel, accommodation, and provisions.

In addition, other F2F technical meetings might be planned throughout the project's life, depending on the project's objectives, needs, and project development status. These F2F technical meetings will be hybrid in order to allow remote connection to those partners that cannot travel to the event.

All F2F meetings will be agreed upon by CERTH and BSC CNS as project coordinators, following WPLs' availability, and will be communicated by the PC via email to all partners 3 months in advance (and, if possible, 6) in order to ensure all partners' attendance and enable proper travel planning.

4.6.2 Online meetings

Regular online meetings will be organised by each board or group:

- ▶ **Work Packages:** Each Work Package Leader / co-Leader will set up regular online monthly meetings with their WP colleagues.
- ▶ **Management Board:** the MB will set up regular project monitoring and technical meetings (ideally per month) to review the Work Packages' progress and the interaction among them.
- ▶ **Scientific Advisory Board:** the SAB will convene at least twice during the project lifespan to assess the project's evolution and check progress.

Each partner in charge of organising the meeting will be responsible for:

- ▶ **Sharing the agenda and relevant documents** with invited participants. These documents should be saved in each pertinent shared folder.
- ▶ **Arranging the video conference call:** any video conference platform that works best for all participating partners can be used. **Zoom** is a recommended option as it offers a stable, trustworthy, and useful connection. Sharing the link with attendees.
- ▶ Sending **calendar invites** to all attendees.

- ▶ Taking **meeting minutes** and keeping track of **attendees**: each WP folder has a subfolder for meetings. All WPLs are invited to take notes.

4.6.3 European Commission (EC) Project Review meetings

EVERSE foresees the following two Project Review Meetings with the European Commission:

- ▶ **Mid-term Review meeting**, M20, venue TBC (probably online)
- ▶ **End Review meeting**, M38, venue TBC

In order to help organise such EC Project Review Meetings and go through all the presentation materials, a Management Board online mock session with all WPLs will be scheduled at least one week before the official date.

The following table contains a summary of the main project meetings that will be organised:

Meeting Type	Responsible	Frequency	Venue
Kick-off Meeting (KoM)	CERTH	Once, M1	Thessaloniki, Greece (hybrid)
General Assembly meetings	Hosting partner (with support from the MB)	Annually	F2F (TBC)
Project monitoring / Technical meetings	Management Board	Monthly	Online / F2F (TBC) (hybrid)
Work Package meetings	WP Leader / co-Leader	Monthly	Online
EC Mid-term Review Meeting	Project Coordinator (with support from the MB)	Once, M20	TBC
EC End Review Meeting	Project Coordinator (with support from the MB)	Once, M38	TBC

Table 4. Summary/Overview project meetings

4.7 Participation in external events

Participation in external events where the project outcomes can be shared with a broader audience is of paramount importance for the European Commission.

All partners are kindly requested to fill the relevant table ("Consortium\5.Meetings\External events\). detailed information about any participation or dissemination activity they are involved in.

4.8 Conflict of Interest

Goodwill to avoid any conflict of interest and to act in good faith is essential for the EVERSE project. When partners identify conflicts of interest that cannot be resolved through bilateral communication, they should immediately bring the issues to the attention of the Project Coordinator. The Project Coordinator working with the MB as necessary will, in turn, bring the issue to the General Assembly for discussion and a vote if required.

4.9 Emergency Procedure

Any event that may jeopardise the overall completion date of the Project should be reported immediately to the PC. The PC working with the MB will endeavour to resolve the issue as soon as possible by calling an emergency General Assembly Meeting as required in order to determine the next steps/mitigation measures.

4.10 Quality Control and Assurance

4.10.1 Project results, expected outcomes and expected impacts

This handbook contributes directly to achieving the operational objectives. It contributes indirectly by providing a working environment that ensures efficient cooperation and focuses on technical work.

The following table summarises the main expected results, against outcomes and impacts:

Project Results	Expected Outcomes	Expected Impacts
<p>#1 RSQkit is the EVERSE knowledge hub resource. As a gateway and search engine to the main results, RSQkit offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ a curated catalogue of best practices and procedures; ○ a catalogue of software and tools to support best practices for high quality software, and support assessment; ○ a catalogue of training resources; ○ a catalogue of training courses; ○ recorded training courses, workshops, conferences, and associated materials. 	<p>#1 Overall measurable improvement of software quality through improved best practices;</p>	<p><u>Scientific</u></p> <p>Impactful cultural and behavioural change in and among research communities, including recognition of research software and the people who build and maintain it, and the quality standards relating to research software</p>

EVERSE-D6.1 Project Handbook and Sustainability Plans for Outputs

<p>#2 Adoption of a common set of the outcomes of the RSQkit, by the RIs and EOSC Science Clusters engaged in the project.</p>	<p>#2 Cultural change in attitudes to research software development, and a growing common culture across research domains and communities;</p>	<p><u>Economic/Societal</u> More efficient use of financial, computational and human resources due to higher quality, more sustainable research software.</p>
<p>#3 Plan the structure and governance of a sustainable Virtual Institute to continue the work of EVERSE, and maintain the community.</p>	<p>#3 Cross-domain scientific collaboration and opportunities;</p>	<p><u>Societal</u> More awareness of the benefits of Open Science.</p>
	<p>#4 Increased sharing of expertise and research software across communities;</p>	
	<p>#5 Improved career opportunities for and RSEs and researchers who code, both in academic research and industry;</p>	
	<p>#6 Software optimised to be more efficient, e.g. for energy consumption, HPC, HTC, etc.</p>	

Table 5. Summary of the Results, Expected Outcomes and Expected Impacts. For reference, please consult table in Grant Agreement – Annex 1 – DoA – Part B

5 Project Monitoring

5.1 Project Follow-up Strategy

The **Management Board** will set up regular meetings (ideally monthly, and at least once every three months) with the aim of monitoring the work progress and the adequate use of resources. This will ensure the timely detection of project challenges and will allow the development of corrective actions and contingency plans for unexpected deviations.

The following sub-sections gather the specific follow-up strategies developed for the Deliverables, Milestones, and Use of Resources as set in the project proposal. The timings of the project's Deliverables and Milestones are visualised in the following Gantt Chart, that is available in the ownCloud shared folder "Consortium\3.Deliverables and Milestones"

WP	Title	M03	M06	M09	M12	M15	M18	M21	M24	M27	M30	M33	M36
WP1	Framework of the European Network of Research Software Quality		MS1.1		D1.1		MS1.2		D1.2		MS1.3		D1.3
1.1	Onboarding support for additional scientific communities established and first communities integrated												
1.2	EVERSE Community Engagement												
1.3	Active European network of Research Software Quality												
WP2	Community-led best practices for developing high-quality research software		MS2.1	D2.1	MS2.2		D2.2		MS2.3		MS2.4	D2.3	D2.4
2.1	Initial collections of additional aspects to enhance software quality												
2.2	Mid-term Report on Knowledge Hub Delivery and Best Practices for Research Software Development												
2.3	Final Report on Knowledge Hub Delivery and Best Practices for Research Software Development												
2.4	Curated Best Practices for Software Quality across Disciplines: Indicators and Implementation Plan for Science Clusters												
WP3	Tools and services for software quality and FAIRness			D3.1		MS3.1	D3.2 / MS3.2		MS3.3		MS3.4		D3.3
3.1	First collection of existing tools and services usable in the Science clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality and FAIRness												
3.2	Catalogue of RSQkit Tools for Assessing and Improving Software Quality and FAIRness												
3.3	Impact of Pipelines and Dashboards on Software Quality: Final Adoption Report												
WP4	EOOSC Science Cluster Pilots and Driver projects				D4.1		D4.2 / MS4.1		D4.3 / MS4.2		MS4.3		D4.4
4.1	Initial list of community established metrics/good practices for evaluating the quality of software as well as established training platforms/recognition activities in the science clusters												
4.2	Engagement and Software Assessment for Researchers (initial demonstrator)												
4.3	Engagement and Software Assessment for Researchers												
4.4	Improved Software Quality through EVERSE												
WP5	Capacity Building and Recognition				D5.1 / MS5.1		D5.2 / MS5.2		MS5.3		MS5.4	D5.3	D5.4
5.1	Landscape analysis of existing rewards and mechanisms for research software and training activities												
5.2	Enhanced and Curated Training Resources Aligned with Software Best Practices: Initial Release												
5.3	Enhanced and Curated Training Resources Aligned with Software Best Practices												
5.4	Recognition Framework for Trainers and RSEs in Research Software Quality												
WP6	Project Management & Coordination		D6.1	D6.2 / D6.3			D6.4						D6.5 / D6.6 / D6.7
6.1	Initial Project Handbook and Sustainability Plans for Outputs												
6.2	Project Data Management Plan and Updates I												
6.3	Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E) Plan												
6.4	Policy Briefing I												
6.5	Project Handbook and Sustainability Plans for Outputs												
6.6	Project Data Management Plan and Updates II												
6.7	Policy Briefing II												

5.1.1 Follow-up of Deliverables

Project Deliverables to the European Commission serve as official outcomes of the technical progress of the Work Packages.

The Deliverable template, which consists of a general deliverable structure and formatting guidelines, is available in the ownCloud shared folder “Consortium\6.Communication\Project templates”

The following table contains the list of the project Deliverables with reference to, among other aspects, the Deliverable Lead Beneficiary and the due dates as in the GA:

D#	WP	Deliverable name	Month Due	Due Date	Lead	Type	Dissemination level
D1.1	1	Onboarding support for additional scientific communities established and first communities integrated	M13	31/3/2025	ELIXIR	R	PU
D1.2	1	EVERSE Community Engagement	M24	28/2/2026	CERN	DEM	PU
D1.3	1	Active European network of Research Software Quality	M36	28/2/2027	BSC CNS	R	PU
D2.1	2	Initial collections of additional aspects to enhance software quality	M09	30/11/2024	BSC CNS	R	PU
D2.2	2	Mid-term Report on Knowledge Hub Delivery and Best Practices for Research Software Development	M18	31/8/2025	BSC CNS	R	PU
D2.3	2	Final Report on Knowledge Hub Delivery and Best Practices for Research Software Development	M34	31/12/2026	NLESC	R	PU
D2.4	2	Curated Best Practices for Software Quality across Disciplines: Indicators and Implementation Plan for Science Clusters	M36	28/2/2027	HZDR	DEM	PU
D3.1	3	First collection of existing tools and services usable in the Science clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality and FAIRness	M09	30/11/2024	NLESC	R	PU
D3.2	3	Catalogue of RSQkit Tools for Assessing and Improving Software Quality and FAIRness	M18	31/8/2025	CNRS	DEM	PU
D3.3	3	Impact of Pipelines and Dashboards on Software Quality: Final Adoption Report	M36	28/2/2027	OPENAIRE MAKE	R	PU
D4.1	4	Initial list of community established metrics/good practices for evaluating the quality of software as well as established training platforms/recognition activities in the science clusters	M12	28/2/2025	UvA	R	PU
D4.2	4	Engagement and Software Assessment for Researchers (initial demonstrator)	M18	31/8/2025	UvA	DEM	PU
D4.3	4	Engagement and Software Assessment for Researchers	M24	28/2/2026	HZDR	DEM	PU

D4.4	4	Improved Software Quality through EVERSE	M36	28/2/2027	ELIXIR	R	PU
D5.1	5	Landscape analysis of existing rewards and mechanisms for research software and training activities	M12	28/2/2025	OPENAIRE MAKE	R	PU
D5.2	5	Enhanced and Curated Training Resources Aligned with Software Best Practices: Initial Release	M18	31/8/2025	UPM	DEM	PU
D5.3	5	Enhanced and Curated Training Resources Aligned with Software Best Practices	M32	30/10/2026	UPM	DEM	PU
D5.4	5	Recognition Framework for Trainers and RSEs in Research Software Quality	M36	28/2/2027	CERN	R	PU
D6.1	6	Initial Project Handbook and Sustainability Plans for Outputs	M04	30/6/2024	CERTH	R	PU
D6.2	6	Project Data Management Plan and Updates I	M06	31/8/2024	CERTH	R	PU
D6.3	6	Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E) Plan	M06	31/8/2024	CERTH	R	PU
D6.4	6	Policy Briefing I	M18	31/8/2025	CERTH	R	PU
D6.5	6	Project Handbook and Sustainability Plans for Outputs	M36	28/2/2027	CERTH	R	PU
D6.6	6	Project Data Management Plan and Updates II	M36	28/2/2027	CERTH	R	PU
D6.7	6	Policy Briefing II	M36	28/2/2027	CERTH	R	PU

Table 6. List of Deliverables

In order to ensure that the deliverables will be submitted to the European Commission on time and properly reviewed against a well-defined set of criteria to meet the minimum quality standards, the following Deliverable Review Process has been put in place:

- ▶ **3 months before due date:** the Project Management Team (PMT) sends a message to both the Work Package Leader (WPL) and the Deliverable Lead Beneficiary (DLB) with the table of exact deadlines to follow and ask them to update the table “EVERSE_Project Deliverables_Milestones Follow-up” with the names of the:
 - ▶ Person that will coordinate the writing (Deliverable Coordinator)
 - ▶ Reviewer + back-up reviewer*.
- ▶ **2 months before due date:** send the first reminder requesting the WPL + DLB to share the Table of Content (ToC) among the Deliverable participating partners + PMT and to confirm the Deliverable Coordinator + Reviewer.
- ▶ **1 month before due date:** send the second reminder to the WPL + DLB + Deliverable Coordinator to seek an update on the writing status.
- ▶ **21 days before due date:** the final draft is shared with both the MB and the Reviewer. The Reviewer takes up to 7 days to review the Deliverable and provide feedback to the Deliverable Coordinator. Then, the Deliverable Coordinator addresses all comments and raises, if necessary, any concerns to the MB.
- ▶ **7 days before due date:** the Deliverable Coordinator shares the final document to the PMT for internal check-up of the formatting. CERTH submits the document in the EC Participant Portal and informs the Consortium members accordingly.

** Every 6 months the project coordinator will suggest a list of reviewers/back-up reviewers for each Deliverable, which will be agreed during a MB meeting.*

Figure 3. Summary of Deliverable Review Process

This task will be coordinated by the PMT and the MB.

Should the Deliverable Lead Beneficiary foresee a delay in submitting the Deliverable, a prior notice of 1 month should be given to the Project Management Team with a written justification and a suggested plan B in order to inform the EC Project Officer and to update the Participant Portal accordingly.

5.1.2 Follow-up of Milestones

A list of Milestones has been developed to help with the project implementation and check its progress. Each Milestone has been equipped with a set of means of verification.

No.	WP	Milestone name	Month Due	Due Date	Lead	Means of Verification
1	1	"Project website, newsletter and social media setup"	M06	31/8/2024	CERN	Demonstrator
2	1	Common activities established with partner organisations, including links to industry	M18	31/8/2025	UEDIN	Report
3	1	Produce a Roadmap to a more permanent European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence	M30	31/8/2026	CERN	Report
4	2	Initial best practices landscaping results	M06	31/8/2024	FAU	Report
5	2	Initial release of the RSQkit	M12	28/2/2025	UPM	Demonstrator
6	2	Initial list of indicators associated with best practices	M24	28/2/2026	SKAO	Report
7	2	Final release of the RSQkit containing curated best practices and associated indicators	M30	31/8/2026	UNIMAN	Demonstrator
8	3	First evaluation of the tools and services in the form of a workshop against WP2 initial best practices (MS2.1) and recommendations to adapt these tools if necessary	M14	30/4/2025	UEDIN	Workshop
9	3	First version of a metadata framework for software quality indicators and of actionable pipelines based on community selected use-cases to assist software developers and maintainers assessing and improving software quality, metadata and FAIRness	M18	31/8/2025	FAU	Demonstrator
10	3	Dashboard prototypes demonstrating capabilities to track software quality and tested in the Science Clusters	M24	28/2/2026	NLESC	Demonstrator
11	3	Demonstration of the outcome of the common framework to the research community, by showing software quality indicators in existing services (such as OpenEBench, WorkflowHub, Research Software Directory, ENVRIHUB, etc) based on the dashboard prototype	M30	31/8/2026	UPM	Demonstrator
12	4	First feedback on the identified common	M18	31/8/2025	UNIMAN	Survey results

		software quality metrics and measurement tools from the science clusters				
13	4	First feedback on the identified common training material from pilot courses in the science clusters	M24	28/2/2026	CU	Survey results
14	4	Science clusters integrated into RSQkit with references to software evaluation dashboards and training material	M30	31/8/2026	UNIMAN	Report and demonstrator
15	5	Mapping of the stocktake of training materials across the training initiatives in the research communities of WP4 and a first assessment on gaps to be filled	M12	28/2/2025	HZDR	Report
16	5	A mechanism for recognition of activities to be easily used in CVs	M18	31/8/2025	UNIPD	Demonstrator
17	5	Prototype of a training catalogue made available to the science clusters with feedback collected on the usability by early adopters	M24	28/2/2026	CNRS	Demonstrator
18	5	Partners outside the consortium have joined the training initiative	M30	31/8/2026	UNILE	Report

Table 7. List of Milestones

The PMT has developed the following Milestones follow-up strategy:

- ▶ **2 months before due date:** the Project Management Team (PMT) communicates in writing with both the Work Package Leader (WPL) and the Milestone Lead Beneficiary (MLB) with the table of exact deadlines to follow and ask them to gather all the information that will need to be uploaded to the Participant Portal, by each Reporting Period.
- ▶ **1 month before due date:** reminder requesting the WPL + MLB to fill the template.
- ▶ **7 days before due date:** the MLB shares with the PMT the filled template and CERTH updates the Participant Portal before the end of each Reporting Period.

Figure 4. Summary of Milestones Review Process

5.1.3 Follow-up of the Use of Resources

The Project Management Team will assist partners in monitoring their adequate use of resources.

To that end, a first close review of the use of resources will be done within M18-M20 during the First Reporting Period in which all partners should have submitted their numbers to the EC. Please find [in this link](#) a detailed explanation of the EC Reporting Process. At that time, pertinent decisions and measures can be taken to address any necessary issues.

Then, in M25-M26 partners will be asked to submit to the PMT an internal financial report with the aim of ensuring that the use of resources is on track as planned and to identify possible deviations and over/under expenditures, with the following information:

- ▶ Person Months per WP
- ▶ Subcontracting costs (if any)
- ▶ Travel and subsistence (if any)
- ▶ Other goods, works, and services (if any)

All partners are reminded of their responsibility for recording working hours for their accounting purposes, detailed non-personnel costs, such as travel and subsistence allowances and equipment, as well as indirect costs. The partner must declare all eligible costs, actual costs, unit costs, and flat-rate costs, even if they exceed the amounts indicated in the budget, as amounts that are not declared in the individual financial statements will not be considered by the eUROPEAN Commission. It is important to highlight that if more budget is claimed beyond what has been originally granted in the GA, this will be at each partner's risk (meaning that the extra amount might be covered if there is extra money in the end if someone else is underspending - but this might not be the case).

5.2 EC Periodic Reports

There are two official reporting periods:

- ▶ **Reporting period 1:** M1-M18 (1 March 2024 to 31 August 2025)
- ▶ **Reporting period 2:** M19-M36 (1 September 2025 to 28 February 2027)

According to the Grant Agreement, the Project Coordinator must submit a periodic report within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. Therefore, the **First Periodic Report** will be due in **M20** and the **Second and Final Periodic Report** will be due in **M38**.

The drafting of these Periodic Reports will be coordinated by the Project Management Team (led by CERTH), where all WPLs will take care of the progress of their Work Packages, with the support of the other involved partners.

For the structure and requirements of these technical and financial reports, see article 21 of the GA.

6 Risk Management

In general, risk management will be the responsibility of the Management Board, and the status of any risk situation will be communicated to the EC via the Periodic Reports, except when there is a clear need for earlier EC intervention upon the decision of the GA.

These risks and their respective mitigating measures are presented in the following table:

No.	WP	Description	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	1	Lack of engagement with scientific software developers and external organisations. Low likelihood, high severity	Partners have excellent working relationships with the appropriate communities and relevant stakeholders
2	1	Divergent ideas on the form and role of the proposed software institute. Low likelihood, low severity	The Network demonstrates what is achievable and useful for all partners, allowing consensus to emerge, through regular engagement activities (such as workshops, webinars, etc)
3	2	New best practices emerge during the project, making our gap analysis obsolete. Medium Likelihood, medium severity	There will be continuous engagement through WP1 to discuss joint efforts, also aligned to the long term sustainability of the project's outputs.
4	2	Inherent differences between fields hamper harmonisation of best practices across fields. Low likelihood, low severity. Inherent differences between fields hamper harmonisation of best practices across fields. Low likelihood, low severity	Domain specific circumstances underpinning certain best practices will be made explicit, leading to a diversified view on software quality, rather than a one-size-fits-all view
5	3	Lack of tools and services to assess, curate and improve software quality in the Science Clusters. Low likelihood, high severity	Partners have excellent working relationships with the Science Clusters and some tools have already been identified
6	3	Failure to successfully implement the proposed technologies. Low likelihood, high severity	Partners have previous experience with the technologies and infrastructures involved
7	4	Poor engagement of Science Clusters members outside EVERSE. Low likelihood, medium severity	Engagement and communication within WP1 and individual use cases for software to be showcased in WP4
8	4	Use cases (subtasks) do not deliver. Low likelihood, high severity	Continuous monitoring the tasks, from the preparation to execution and delivery, including awareness of developments in WP1-3
9	5	Training materials do not reflect the needs of specific communities. Medium likelihood, medium severity	Develop comparison studies to analyse the impact of recognition frameworks in a researchers' career
10	6	Large consortia could be difficult to manage and coordinate effectively. Low likelihood, medium severity	The project consortium has many years experience in managing very large, diverse, distributed collaborations (e.g. WLCG, ELIXIR, and many more), including experience in the cluster projects, and joint cluster actions
11	6	Failure of the UK to sign Association agreement to Horizon Europe puts EC funding for UK partners at risk. Low likelihood, medium severity	Project management and UK partners will closely monitor the progress of negotiations and follow advice from UK Research Councils (UKRI). This proposal will likely be submitted

			before the outcome of Association is known, but in the event that the UK has not Associated to Horizon Europe at the time of project start, UK partners will remain integral to the project and funding provided via UKRI administered guarantee fund rather than Horizon Europe
--	--	--	--

Table 8. List of Critical Risks and Mitigation Measures

With the aim of ensuring that any risk or challenge is timely and effectively addressed, the following Risk Follow-up Strategy has been set up:

- ▶ **M06-8:** once the project activities have started, a dedicated Management Board meeting will analyse and assess the proposed list of risks and their mitigation measures with the aim to verify that they stay relevant, update them if necessary, and to identify new ones.
- ▶ **M14:** the MB discusses, ahead of the upcoming Mid-term EC Review, the state of the identified risks and applies any mitigation measures when needed.
- ▶ **M26:** the MB discusses, 10 months before the project finishes, if there are any risks that need to be handled and apply any mitigation measures when needed.
- ▶ **M34:** the MB discusses, closer to the second and final reporting period, the state of the identified risks and applies any mitigation measures when needed.

The following figure contains a summary of the Risk follow-up strategy.

Figure 5. Summary of Risk follow-up strategy

7 Intellectual Property Rights and Knowledge Management

An Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is an important tool to protect the value generated by the project. Knowledge and IPR management objectives, principles, and roles are foreseen in the Grant Agreement as well as in the Consortium Agreement.

The background of each partner has been included in Attachment 1 of the EVERSE Consortium Agreement at the beginning of the project. Each partner owns the results, specified in Section 8 of the CA according to Article 26 of the Grant Agreement. In addition, the joint ownership of the results, transfer, and dissemination are defined in the same section of the CA.

Throughout the project duration, Partners should report any potential project-generated result to the Project Coordinator in order to facilitate any further exploitation opportunity once the project will end.

During the project and for the period of one year after the end of the project the dissemination of own Results by one or several Partners including, but not restricted to, publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 29.1 of the Grant Agreement subject to the following provisions.

Each partner shall implement its tasks in accordance with the CA and shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that its acts within the Project do not knowingly infringe third-party property rights. Access Rights to results and background needed for the non-commercial performance of the own work of a partner under the Project are requested and granted on a royalty-free, non-transferable basis.

8 Acronyms and Abbreviations

EVERSE	European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
--------	---

A	Affiliated Entities
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of the Action (Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement)
DL	Deliverable Lead Beneficiary
E	European Commission
E	Expected Impact
E	Expected Outcomes
E	European Union
G	General Assembly / Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
M	Month
MB	Management Board
MLB	Milestone Lead Beneficiary
MS	Milestone
PMT	Project Management Team
W	Work Package
WP	Work Package

9 Annexes

9.1 Staff effort per participant

STAFF EFFORT PER PARTICIPANT (in person-months)							
Partner	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	Total
1-CERTH	6.00	12.00	6.00	9.00	12.00	24.00	69.00
2-BSC CNS		21.00	18.00	9.00	6.00	9.00	63.00
3-CERN	21.00		12.00		26.00	4.00	63.00
4-CNRS	6.00	12.00	21.00		24.00	4.00	67.00
5-FAU		12.00	12.00			2.00	26.00
6-SKAO	6.00	20.00	10.00			2.00	38.00
7-ELIXIR	18.00			5.00	3.00	2.00	28.00
8-UvA	4.00	4.00	6.00	16.00	4.00	2.00	36.00
9-HZDR			12.00	18.00	15.00	4.00	49.00
10-NLESC	6.00	18.00	18.00		6.00	4.00	52.00
11-UPM	3.00	9.00	9.00	6.00	21.00	4.00	52.00
12-UNIPD		3.00			15.00	2.00	20.00
13-UNILE	5.00				13.00	2.00	20.00
14-OPENAIRE AMKE	12.00	2.00	5.00	10.00	10.00	1.00	40.00
14.1-ARC		4.00	5.00		5.00	1.00	15.00
15-CU	12.00	6.00	6.00	18.00	10.00	2.00	54.00
Total Person-Months	99.00	123.00	140.00	91.00	170.00	69.00	692.00

9.2 Project Months – Calendar months

Year	Project Month	Calendar Month
2024	M1	1/3/2024
	M2	1/4/2024
	M3	1/5/2024
	M4	1/6/2024
	M5	1/7/2024
	M6	1/8/2024
	M7	1/9/2024
	M8	1/10/2024
	M9	1/11/2024
	M10	1/12/2024
2025	M11	1/1/2025
	M12	1/2/2025
	M13	1/3/2025
	M14	1/4/2025
	M15	1/5/2025
	M16	1/6/2025
	M17	1/7/2025
	M18	1/8/2025
	M19	1/9/2025
	M20	1/10/2025
	M21	1/11/2025
	M22	1/12/2025
2026	M23	1/1/2026
	M24	1/2/2026
	M25	1/3/2026
	M26	1/4/2026
	M27	1/5/2026
	M28	1/6/2026
	M29	1/7/2026
	M30	1/8/2026
	M31	1/9/2026
	M32	1/10/2026
	M33	1/11/2026
	M34	1/12/2026
2027	M35	1/1/2027
	M36	1/2/2027

9.3 Work Packages, Tasks, Deliverables

WP	Deliverable	Title	Deliverable Lead Beneficiary / Partners involved in task
1	D1.1	Onboarding support for additional scientific communities established and first communities integrated	ELIXIR/ CERN, SKAO, CNRS-IJCLab, OpenAIRE , ELIXIR, UPM, NLeSC, UniSalento, UEDIN
1	D1.2	EVERSE Community Engagement	ELIXIR/ OpenAIRE ,UvA, CNRS-IJCLab,CU
1	D1.3	Active European network of Research Software Quality	CERN/ NLeSC, UEDIN, SKAO, CERTH, OpenAIRE, UvA, ELIXIR, CU
2	D2.1	Initial collections of additional aspects to enhance software quality	BSC CNS/FAU, UPM, CERTH, UNIMAN, NLeSC, ARC, OpenAIRE, CNRS-LAPP, SKAO, UvA, CU, UEDIN
2	D2.2	Mid-term Report on Knowledge Hub Delivery and Best Practices for Research Software Development	BSC CNS/UPM, UNIMAN, FAU, NLeSC, CNRS-LAPP, SKAO, CU, UEDIN, UniPD
2	D2.3	Final Report on Knowledge Hub Delivery and Best Practices for Research Software Development	BSC CNS/ NLeSC , SKAO ,CERTH, ARC, OpenAIRE, CNRS-LAPP, UPM, UEDIN, CU
2	D2.4	Curated Best Practices for Software Quality across Disciplines: Indicators and Implementation Plan for Science Clusters	NLeSC/ BSC CNS/UPM, UNIMAN, FAU, CNRS-LAPP, SKAO, CU, UEDIN, UniPD
3	D3.1	First collection of existing tools and services available in the Science clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality and FAIRness	HZDR/UEDIN , SKAO ,NLeSC, UPM, FAU, UEDIN, CNRS-LAPP, HZDR, BSC CNS, ARC
3	D3.2	Catalogue of RSQkit Tools for Assessing and Improving Software Quality and FAIRness	NLeSC/BSC CNS, FAU, UNIMAN, CU, UPM, CERN, CNRS-LAPP, HZDR, ARC
3	D3.3	Impact of Pipelines and Dashboards on Software Quality:Final Adoption Report	CNRS/NLeSC, UPM, UNIMAN, CU, CERTH, UEDIN, CERN, BSC CNS
4	D4.1	Initial list of community established metrics/good practices for evaluating the quality of software as well as established training platforms/recognition activities in the science clusters	OPENAIRE/UvA, UPM, BSC CNS, CERTH, CU, ELIXIR-Hub
4	D4.2	Engagement and Software Assessment for Researchers (initial demonstrator)	UvA/UNIMAN, HZDR , BSC CNS, CERTH, CU, ELIXIR-Hub, OpenAIRE, UPM
4	D4.3	Engagement and Software Assessment for Researchers	UvA/ OPENAIRE, UPM, BSC CNS, CERTH, CU, ELIXIR-Hub
4	D4.4	Improved Software Quality through EVERSE	HZDR/ UvA,UNIMAN,BSC CNS, CERTH, CU, ELIXIR-Hub, OpenAIRE, UPM
5	D5.1	Landscape analysis of existing rewards and mechanisms for research software and training activities	OPENAIRE MAKE/HZDR, CNRS, UPM, CERN, NLeSC, UniSalento, ELIXIR-Hub, UvA , CU
5	D5.2	Enhanced and Curated Training Resources Aligned with Software Best Practices:Initial Release	UPM/UniPD,OpenAIRE,HZDR,UPM, CERTH, CU, UniSalento, CNRS
5	D5.3	Enhanced and Curated Training Resources	UPM/UniSalento, CERTH, HZDR, UPM,UniPD,

		Aligned with Software Best Practices	NLeSC, CERN,CNRS,BSC CNS
5	D5.4	Recognition Framework for Trainers and RSEs in Research Software Quality	CERN/UPM,UniPD,OpenAIRE,HZDR,UPM, CERTH, CU, UniSalento, CNRS
6	D6.1	Initial Project Handbook and Sustainability Plans for Outputs	CERTH/BSC CNS
6	D6.2	Project Data Management Plan and Updates I	CERTH/ BSC CNS
6	D6.3	Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E) Plan	CERTH/ BSC CNS
6	D6.4	Policy Briefing I	CERTH/ BSC CNS
6	D6.5	Project Handbook and Sustainability Plans for Outputs	CERTH/ BSC CNS
6	D6.6	Project Data Management Plan and Updates II	CERTH/ BSC CNS
6	D6.7	Policy Briefing II	CERTH/ BSC CNS